

Physico-Chemical Study of Vivianite

BHUPATI K. BANERJEE*

Research & Development, Fertilizer (P & D) India Ltd., Sindri-828 122, India

Manuscript received 18 June 1979, revised 19 November 1979, accepted 9 July 1980

The present paper embodies a critical discussion about the structure of a phosphatic mineral, vivianite, with particular reference of the state of aggregation of its iron ion. The magnetic moment, electronic and infrared spectral studies have been reported. All these findings have been discussed from the point of view of its structure.

THE vivianite is a phosphatic mineral of iron having the chemical formula as $\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

It occurs as a sort of clay like blue pigments of fine crystalline aggregates distributed in diverse places in nature like the coal seams, bog-iron ore, etc. Further the formation of vivianite on ancient buried iron objects in peaty soil¹ and in association with the devitrified products of antique glasses buried in a humus-rich soil² is also reported in the literature. The origin of its blue colouration has been attributed to the oxidation of ferrous to ferric iron. The object of the present work is to furnish some crystallo-chemical information to that end.

The crystal structure of vivianite was determined by Mori and Ito³. It belongs to a monoclinic crystal class with the following crystallographic details :

$$a_0 = 10.08 \text{ \AA}, b = 13.43 \text{ \AA}, c = 4.70 \text{ \AA}, \beta = 104^\circ.30'$$

with 2 molecules per unit cell.

The structure is built up of single and double octahedral groups of oxygen and H_2O around Fe; and the phosphorus atoms are tetrahedrally surrounded by oxygen atoms. For the exhaustive details of its structural characteristics, the original paper of Mori and Ito³ can be referred to. Some interesting accounts of its thermal characteristics are also reported in the literature⁴⁻⁶. It has a strong endothermic peak at 250° , followed by an exothermic peak at 650° .

Experimental

The mineral under investigation was collected as a discrete entity in coal fissures from a coal seam (Purushottampur) of Ranigunj coal field area. It was obtained in sufficient quantity for the present experimental purposes. It was also distributed as blue spots scattered over the surfaces of numerous coal chunks. Its composition was closely approximating to that of vivianite, $\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the material, finely ground, was obtained in a cylindrical camera of radius 114.6 mm using $\text{FeK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.937 \text{ \AA}$) radiation.

Magnetic measurement of the specimen was made by a sensitive Curie-balance at different temperatures ranging from 304.2°K to 90.0°K .

The electronic spectra of the compound $\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were recorded (Fig. 2a and 2b) on a Beckman DB Spectrophotometer.

The infrared spectra of the compound were recorded on Beckman IR-20 model spectrophotometer using KBr pellet.

Results and Discussion

The identification of the crystalline phases was made by the usual method of Hanawalt *et al.*⁷. The 'd' values of vivianite, $\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (vide A. S. T. M., Card Index, No. 3-0070) with the

Fig. 1. $\frac{1}{\chi_a}$ against $T/^\circ\text{K}$

* For correspondence : 2A, Lansdowne Lane, Calcutta-700 026,

Fig. 2a—The electronic spectra of the vivianite.

Fig. 2b—The electronic spectra of the vivianite.

Fig. 3. The infrared spectra of the vivianite.

spacing of first three strong lines are 6.80\AA (100), 2.97\AA (67) and 2.71\AA (67), with the relative intensity shown in the parenthesis. The evidence of the presence of any other phase was not found.

To obtain an insight into the colour problem of vivianite in relation to the valency state of iron, the usual magnetic method of analysis was extended to the above problem. The nature of bondings of iron ion with its surrounding ions, its coordination number, valency, etc., have a direct influence on the magnetic property of the element. The substance is found to be paramagnetic with the mass susceptibility value of 67.05×10^{-6} C.G.S. units at 304.2°K .

Taking into consideration the molecular formula of the substance as $\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and making diamagnetic correction, the mass susceptibility K_{Fe} (for single ion) comes to 11294×10^{-6} C.G.S. units at 304.2°K . The moment value of iron is found to be 5.28 Bohr/magneton.

It would be interesting to compare this value with the theoretical moment value of ferrous and ferric ions. The ferrous ions have a theoretical spin only moment value of 4.90 Bohr magneton, while ferric ions, with one more unpaired electron, have a moment value of 5.92 Bohr magneton. Again the variation of the square of the effective moment value (P_{eff}^2) of iron in experimental specimen from room temperature to 90°K is shown in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Experimental Specimen				Typical Ferrous salt $\text{FeSO}_4(\text{NH}_4)\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ after Bose ¹⁶	
Temp. ($^\circ\text{K}$)	$\chi_a \times 10^6$ CGS unit	$\chi_m \times 10^6$ corr. CGS unit	P_{eff}^2	Temp. ($^\circ\text{K}$)	P_{eff}^2
304.2	67.05	33886.6	27.74	296.8	28.49
262.1	77.07	38910.8	28.10	182.5	28.57
204.0	100.44	50637.3	27.75	84.8	27.13
106.7	123.975	62444.9	26.96		
142.3	139.85	70407.4	26.72		
123.5	160.723	80885.1	26.83		
109.1	181.48	91299.4	26.76		
90.0	219.55	110400.3	26.69		

Diamagnetic corr. = 243×10^{-6} CGS unit.

A plot of $\frac{1}{\chi_a}$ against T/K° (Fig. 1) is linear with zero θ_p value, indicating P_{eff}^2 is independent of temperature.

The variation of $P_{\text{eff}}^2 - T$ value of the experimental specimen is similar to that of the ionic ferrous salt (Table 1) and its variation of P_{eff}^2 with temperature is small. As such the origin of its blue colour due to oxidation of ferrous to ferric iron (which is believed by some workers) is not evident from the present experimental results because iron exists in ferrous state in the mineral concerned.

The electronic spectra of the compound show absorption bands at 325 nm, 380 nm and 508 nm which is analogous to the absorption spectra of Fe^{2+} in a weak field of octahedral symmetry reported earlier⁸⁻¹⁰. Low and Weger¹¹, deduced the complete matrices for the energy level splitting of d^6 configuration (^5D ground state) in weak octahedral field. The first transition band ($^5\text{T}_{2g} \rightarrow ^5\text{E}_g$) which is reported at about 10000 cm^{-1} in case of aquo iron(II) complex is found to be absent in the present compound. The observed

spectra show marked departure from reported one¹¹. So the splitting of the electronic absorption bands in this may be attributed entirely to the splitting of excited state in this distorted ligand field.

The i.r. spectra of the $\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with tentative assignment of the absorption bands has been compared with the spectra of ortho phosphoric acid¹². The spectra (Fig. 3) show two strong bands at 1120 and 1090 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to the ionic phosphate vibration (P-O vibration)¹³⁻¹⁵. The bands in similar position (1150-1000 cm^{-1}) are reported in case of tribasic derivatives of orthophosphoric acid. The difference in the nature of P-O absorption bands in the present compounds from ortho phosphoric acid is due to bonding between P-O group and Fe^{+2} ion. The absorption bands at 3410 cm^{-1} and 1640 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the compound, correspond to OH stretching and bending vibration of the water of crystallization. In addition to above bands, a very sharp medium strong band at 3600 cm^{-1} due to presence of free OH stretching, has appeared. The sharpness of water absorption bands at 3410 cm^{-1} and 3600 cm^{-1} and high value of their OH stretching frequency ($>3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicate that apparently there is very little hydrogen bonding in the compound.

References

1. T. W. FARRER, L. BIEK and F. WORMWELL, *J. Appl. Chem. (Lond)*, 1953, **3**, 80.
2. W. GEILMAN, *Glas. Tech. Ber.*, 1956, **24**, 145.
3. H. MORI and T. ITO, *Acta Cryst.*, 1950, **3**, 1.
4. R. L. MANLY (Jr), *Amer. Mineral*, 1950, **36**, 108.
5. A. GEITH MOHAMED, *Amer. Mineral*, 1953, **38**, 612.
6. R. PULOU, *Compt. rend.*, 1955, **241**, 221.
7. J. D. HANAWALT, H. W. RINN and L. K. FREVEL, *Indus. Eng. Chem. (Anal. Ed.)*, 1938, **10**, 457.
8. F. A. COTTON and M. D. MEYERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5023.
9. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta. Chim. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 1502.
10. C. FURLANI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1957, **87**, 371.
11. W. LOW and M. WEGER, *Phys. Rev.*, 1960, **118**, 1119, 1130.
12. D. E. CORBRIDGE and E. J. LOWE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **493**, 4555.
13. J. L. BELLAMY and L. BEECHER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1701.
14. F. A. MILLER and C. H. WILKINS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 1253.
15. F. VRATNY, M. DILLING, F. GUGLIOTA and C. N. R. RAO, *J. Sci. Ind. Research (India)*, 1961, **20B**, 590.
16. A. BOSE, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1948, **22**, 483.